

MODERN PROBLEMS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418469>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-December 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15- December 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 21- December 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Russian language, teaching, creative and innovative approach, students of non-linguistic universities, problems and solutions, colloquial speech.

ABSTRACT

This article examines modern problems of teaching the Russian language and the use of a creative and innovative approach by Russian language teachers when teaching students at non-linguistic universities, as well as the use of texts, debates, and discussions in the development of spoken language among students, taking into account their levels of language knowledge.

Education at the present stage takes its cue from a comprehensively developed personality. The realities of life in society are such that there is an understanding of the need to educate a creative, receptive, and emotionally responsive person. It is creativity that distinguishes man from a number of living beings. Today, there is a disagreement between the urgent need to create everything necessary to develop and further improve the teaching of the Russian language to students at non-linguistic universities. Modern problems of teaching the Russian language at a non-linguistic university are not found in the specialized literature in an unchanged form. The student's level of knowledge of a foreign language, in our case Russian, also leaves much to be desired.

When solving the problems of teaching the Russian language to students of non-linguistic universities, on the basis of colloquial speech using various texts in their specialty, the concept of "colloquial speech" primarily as an assessment scale is not enough, since this scale largely states the level, but does not create conditions for its improvement. Consequently, in the methodology of teaching spoken language, an approach is needed that would combine both evaluative and developmental, teaching components.

We propose to recognize the consideration of colloquial speech as a culture of speech activity as the most accurate and methodologically productive approach, focusing on modern problems of teaching the Russian language at a non-linguistic university. Thus, the culture of speech activity presupposes the conscious and purposeful activity of students and combines all types of colloquial speech. In this context, from the point of view of culture, not only the product is assessed, but also the process and the result of spoken speech activity.

And it is this approach that best meets the needs of modern processes in the field of education, aimed at raising the level of the general culture of students. It is no coincidence that the competency model, enshrined in

the subject program, on the basis of which colloquial speech is developed, necessarily includes general cultural competencies necessary for representatives of all specialties.

The willingness and ability to conduct a dialogue, listen and hear, speak publicly, discuss various professional and social problems, conduct disputes - these are all key competencies, the most difficult of which is the ability to competently resolve disagreements associated with discussions, polemics and debates. What makes discussions and debates an effective means of improving spoken language when studying the Russian language in non-linguistic universities? These speech genres provide invaluable assistance, mainly in the development of the extremely important from the point of view of speech culture, the ability to formulate one's position and not only prove it, but also convince oneself that one is right, construct verified logically reasoned texts, select and formulate convincing arguments, build them in the most advantageous order for the speaker, take into account their strength relative to a given audience (addressee), illustrate these arguments with examples, use various means of demonstration, giving even greater persuasiveness to the entire text, etc.

In preparation for a discussion or debate, during its conduct and analysis of the results, non-linguistic students practice all the basic actions and operations characteristic of speech activity, to implement all the norms of communication and literary language. At different stages of spoken speech activity, participants in a dispute need to use both written types of speech activity (when preparing their statements, when selecting material, etc.) and oral ones - in the discussions or debates themselves. It is also important that the nature of statements and the increased speech responsibility inherent in such situations also develops the highest possible control of all components of spoken language. It is obvious that all of the listed skills are extremely necessary for every university graduate, even non-linguistic ones, and that the inclusion of discussions and debates in the list of basic general cultural competencies only emphasizes their importance. It is no coincidence that discussion and debate in many European education systems are also recognized as one of the leading teaching methods.

What should a teacher keep in mind when using various types of argument and discussion in teaching as one of the modern problems in the study of the Russian language (RL), especially in non-linguistic universities?

First of all, there is no identity in the purposes and nature of these elements of colloquial speech. As is known, discussion and polemic are types of dispute and differ primarily in goals: discussion is conducted to clarify the truth, and polemic, as a hostile dispute, is conducted to achieve victory in it. Other differences follow from this main difference. The advantage of each participant can be achieved only by belittling the other (others), which is always invariably accompanied by a violation of both ethical and communicative norms of speech. This determines the effectiveness of polemics as a form of educational activity mainly among those students for whom it is especially important to develop self-control.

Discussion is a genre of public debate that, compared to polemics, has a number of advantages for educational purposes. Since in a discussion, opponents argue in order to achieve the truth, this significantly develops its communicative orientation and attention to other participants in communication - opponents, proponents and spectators. A significant advantage of the discussion relative to other colloquial speech genres that require the

creation of an argumentative text, of course, is the desire of all participants for maximum persuasiveness, for which they use various options for methods and types of evidence to the greatest extent.

However, both in the process and as a result of the discussion, the greatest polarization of the positions of the participants invariably occurs, which is due to the fact that, trying to convince others of their rightness, rhetoricians first of all further convince themselves and their opponents of it. The need to confront opponents also adds to the desire to defend one's point of view and not agree with them on anything. All this together, as a rule, leads to the fact that the discussion participants become even more irreconcilable.

As a result, opponents focus not on contradictions, but on supplementing or adjusting ideas about one or another aspect of the problem, and ultimately on finding the optimal way to solve the problem. In the course of debates, the participants of which, as a rule, perceive each other as partners, there is a convergence of initially opposing positions and a softening of the categorical statements.

The differences between debate and discussion pose the problem of choosing the most appropriate genre for the teacher as an active innovative form of conducting classes. To do this, it is important to assess what the depth of consideration of the topic chosen by students should be: debates allow you to consider issues from several sides, what is the real ratio of adherents of both points of view, if they are approximately equal, a full-fledged discussion is possible, if not, it is better to prefer debates.

Students from non-linguistic universities are offered a choice of various topics for debate or discussion during group work or presentation of independent work, reports and abstracts:

1. The most beautiful cities in the world.
2. Art. Modern Art.
3. Wonders of the world
4. Formation of self-esteem of a preschooler in the process of creative activity
5. The family is the unit of society, etc.

It is also necessary to take into account the number of students in the group.

In a discussion, a situation often occurs when the main arguments FOR and AGAINST are expressed in the first minutes. And then the rest of the students begin to either repeat what was said or refuse to speak on the grounds that they do not know what else can be said on the topic of discussion. This does not happen in debates, since the discussion is divided into several stages - sub-questions.

Thus, modern problems of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities are solved with the help of modern methods based on the creative method of the teacher, so each of the methods and methods we have considered has enormous potential for improving the teaching of the Russian language, as well as speech among students of non-linguistic universities, but the effectiveness their use will largely be determined on the basis of the language level of the non-philologist student.

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